

CONDENSATION OF *o*-, *m*- AND *p*- THIOCRESOLS WITH *o*-BROMONITROBENZENE, 2:5-DICHLORONITROBENZENE AND 2:5-DIBROMONITROBENZENE.

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Thiocresols (*o*-, *m*- and *p*-) have been condensed with *o*-bromonitrobenzene, 2:5-dichloronitrobenzene and 2:5-dibromonitrobenzene as a result of which 2'-nitro-2-methyldiphenyl sulphide, 2'-nitro-4-methyldiphenyl sulphide, 2'-nitro-4-methyldiphenyl sulphide, 4-chloro-2-nitro-4'-methyldiphenyl sulphide, 4-bromo-2-nitro-4'-methyldiphenyl sulphide and 4-chloro-2-nitro-2'-methyldiphenyl sulphide have been obtained.

o-Nitrophenyl thioethers and their alkyl and halogen derivatives being required for another piece of research, a reference to literature revealed that very few compounds of this series are known. Mauthner (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 3597) obtained 2-nitrodiphenyl sulphide by the condensation of sodium thiophenate and *o*-nitrobromobenzene in presence of copper powder; the same compound has been obtained by boiling sodium thiophenate and *o*-bromonitrobenzene in alcohol (Bourgeois and Uber, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1911, iv, 9, 947) and by the action of thiophenol, potassium hydroxide and *o*-chloronitrobenzene in presence of copper-bronze (Roberts and Turner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1207). Mauthner also obtained *o*-nitrophenyl-*o*-tolyl sulphide from sodium *o*-thiocresolate and *o*-bromonitrobenzene. This compound is wrongly described as 4-nitro-*o*-phenyl-*o*-tolyl sulphide and 4-nitro-2-methyldiphenyl sulphide (Beilstein-Prager-Jacobson, "Organische Chemie," Vol. VI, p. 371). Loudon and Robson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 242) have also obtained 4-chloro-2-nitro-4-methyldiphenyl sulphide by condensing 2:5-dichloronitrobenzene with *p*-thiocresol in alcohol.

In the experiments described in this paper the following condensation products have been obtained.—

2'-Nitro-2-methyldiphenyl sulphide, m.p. 86°, b.p. 210-15°/18 mm.

2'-Nitro-3-methyldiphenyl sulphide, m.p. 86-86.5°; b.p. 222°/18 mm.

2'-Nitro-4-methyldiphenyl sulphide, m.p. 87.5°.

4-Chloro-2-nitro-4'-methyldiphenyl sulphide, m.p. 121°.

4-Bromo-2-nitro-4'-methyldiphenyl sulphide, m.p. 124°.

4-Chloro-2-nitro-2'-methyldiphenyl sulphide.

The products obtained with *m*-thiocresol are liquids and not in good quantities. It has not yet been possible to separate these products and obtain them in sufficient quantities for further investigation.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

2'-Nitro-2-methyldiphenyl Sulphide.—*o*-Thiocresol (31 g.), *o*-bromonitrobenzene (51 g.) and copper-bronze (2 g.) were added to a warm solution of potassium hydroxide (10 g. in 10 c.c. water) and the solution refluxed on a sand-bath for 4½ hours at about 180°. It was then allowed to cool when the product solidified to a greenish black mass. The product was extracted successively for 4 times with carbon tetrachloride (50 c.c.; 30 c.c.; 20 c.c., 10 c.c.) and the whole extract washed first with 15% potassium hydroxide solution to remove the unacted *o*-thiocresol and then with water, dried over fused calcium chloride and distilled under reduced pressure. The fraction distilling at 210-15°/16 mm. solidified to a yellow mass and gave needle-shaped yellow crystals (20 g.) on crystallisation from carbon tetrachloride, m.p. 86°. It is readily soluble in carbon tetrachloride, insoluble in petroleum ether, slightly soluble in alcohol and very easily in carbon disulphide and benzene. (Found: S, 12·8. C₁₂H₁₁O₂NS requires S, 13·06 per cent).

2'-Nitro-3-methyldiphenyl Sulphide.—*o*-Bromonitrobenzene (12·5 g.), *m*-thiocresol (8 g.) and copper-bronze (0·5 g.) were added to a solution of sodium hydroxide (2·4 g.) in water (1-2 c.c.) and the solution refluxed for 4 hours at about 180° and the product treated as in the preceding case and distilled under reduced pressure. The fraction distilling at 222°/18 mm. solidified to a yellow solid mass. It was crystallised from carbon tetrachloride, m.p. 86·5°, yield 3·5 g. (Found S, 12·5. C₁₂H₁₁O₂NS requires S, 13·06 per cent).

2'-Nitro-4-methyldiphenyl Sulphide.—*o*-Bromonitrobenzene (50 g.), *p*-thiocresol (31 g.), potassium hydroxide (14 g.) and copper-bronze (2 g.) were treated as above for 3½ hours on a sand-bath at about 200° and treated as in the preceding cases and the solid product boiled with animal charcoal and then crystallised from carbon tetrachloride when yellow prisms were obtained, m.p. 87·5°. (Found: S, 13·1. C₁₂H₁₁O₂N S requires S, 13·06 per cent).

4-Chloro-2-nitro-4'-methyldiphenyl Sulphide.—*p*-Thiocresol (2 g.), 2:5-dichloronitrobenzene (2 g.), potassium hydroxide (0·6 g.) and water (1 c.c.) were refluxed on a sand-bath for 6 hours at about 180° and the product allowed to cool when a red solid mass was obtained. It was extracted thrice with carbon tetrachloride, washed with 15% potassium hydroxide solution and then with water, dried over fused calcium chloride and the solvent distilled off. The residue was crystallised from glacial acetic acid when orange prisms were obtained, m.p. 121°. It is easily soluble in warm carbon tetrachloride, soluble even in cold in benzene and carbon disulphide;

it is less soluble in petroleum ether, yield 1.7 g. (Found: S, 11.1. $C_{13}H_{10}O_2NCIS$ requires S, 11.4 per cent).

4-Bromo-2-nitro-4'-methyldiphenyl Sulphide.—2:5-Dichloronitrobenzene (2 g.) on similar treatment with *p*-thiocresol (3 g.) and potassium hydroxide (0.6 g.) in presence of copper-bronze gave orange-red crystals, m.p. 124°. It is very soluble in benzene and carbon disulphide, soluble on warming in carbon tetrachloride, much less soluble in petroleum ether, yield 1.8 g. (Found: Br, 24.4; S, 9.2. $C_{13}H_{10}O_2NBrS$ requires Br, 24.7; S, 9.8 per cent).

4-Chloro-2'-nitro-2-methyldiphenyl Sulphide.—*o*-Thiocresol (4 g.) and 2:5-dichloronitrobenzene (4 g.) and potassium hydroxide (1.2 g.) on similar treatment gave a distillate boiling at 200-205°/18 mm. which solidified slowly into bright yellow crystals, m.p. 82.5°. It is slightly soluble in rectified spirit and petroleum ether, more on warming. (Found: Cl, 12.3. $C_{13}H_{10}O_2NCIS$ requires Cl, 12.7 per cent).

4-Bromo-2-nitro-4'-methyldiphenyl Sulphone.—Potassium permanganate solution (0.7 g. in 100 c.c. of water) was added little by little to a solution of 4-bromo-2-nitro-4'-methyldiphenyl sulphide (1 g.) in glacial acetic acid and the excess of potassium permanganate was removed by passing sulphur dioxide and the whole allowed to stand overnight when a white precipitate was obtained. It was crystallised from carbon tetrachloride as beautiful needles, m.p. 132°. It turns pinkish on heating. (Found: S, 8.5. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4NBrS$ requires S, 8.9 per cent).